

1 **Golden rules for building sustainable bioinformatics capacity using**
2 **Nextflow and nf-core with a focus on early-mid career researchers: The**
3 **Kids Research Institute Australia, case report.**

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36 **Abstract**

37 The increasing adoption of high-throughput "omics" technologies has heightened the demand
38 for standardized, scalable, and reproducible bioinformatics workflows. Nextflow and nf-core provide
39 a robust framework for researchers, particularly early- and mid-career researchers (EMCRs), to
40 navigate complex data analysis. At The Kids Research Institute Australia, we implemented a structured
41 approach to bioinformatics capacity building using these tools. This perspective presents nine practical
42 “golden” rules that facilitated the successful adoption of Nextflow and nf-core, addressing
43 implementation, knowledge gaps, resource allocation, and community support. Our experience serves
44 as a guide for institutions aiming to establish sustainable bioinformatics capabilities and empower
45 EMCRs.

46

47 **Introduction**

48 The demand for researchers skilled in bioinformatics has surged due to the increasing adoption
49 of high-throughput “omics” technologies, presenting both, opportunities and challenges. Researchers
50 without formal training in programming or workflow engines must now analyze high-dimensional
51 datasets using various tools, while ensuring analysis are reproducible across computational
52 environments. This has highlighted a need for omics data workflows that are standardized, scalable,
53 and reproducible. In this context, we aimed to provide early- and mid-career researchers (EMCRs) with
54 opportunities to gain knowledge and establish a bioinformatics support system (Woelmer et al., 2021)
55 using workflow managers like Nextflow and the nf-core community.

56 Nextflow is a workflow management system designed to streamline bioinformatics research by
57 composing multiple tools into a single pipeline (Di Tommaso et al., 2017). Its flexibility, portability
58 and scalability ranges from local servers, high-performance clusters, and cloud environments with
59 minimal reconfiguration. Nextflows native task parallelization, makes it ideal for handling high-
60 volume of datasets originating from modern "omics" technologies (Dai and Shen, 2022). In addition,
61 the nf-core community enhances the Nextflow ecosystem by connecting users through hackathons,
62 seminars, training, and collaborative platforms like Slack (Ewels et al., 2020; Langer et al., 2024). For
63 newcomers, this support is invaluable for troubleshooting and professional growth. Additionally, nf-
64 core community develops and maintains pipelines used across different fields of life sciences. Each
65 pipeline follows strict guidelines to ensure robustness, reproducibility, and ease of use, which are key
66 features for EMCRs entering bioinformatics.

67 For institutions and researchers in "omics" studies, adopting Nextflow and nf-core is strategic.
68 These tools enable management of high-throughput data, effective collaboration, and reproducible
69 results, ensuring continued scientific advancement. This is especially crucial for EMCRs driving
70 innovation. By integrating these tools into training, institutions can better prepare researchers to meet
71 modern bioinformatics challenges (Stephens et al., 2015).

72 Here, we share our experience at The Kids Research Institute Australia (The Kids), a research
73 institution in Perth (Australia) with a diverse workforce and a strong commitment to building EMCR
74 expertise in computational biology. The Theme Collaboration Group, a multidisciplinary team across
75 The Kids, played a key role in shaping this initiative (Supplemental Data S1). We outline practical
76 "golden" rules essential for adopting and implementing Nextflow (Table 1). These guidelines aim to
77 help other institutions establish sustainable and robust bioinformatics capabilities, enabling researchers
78 to fully leverage Nextflow and nf-core for scientific discovery. Figure 1 summarizes the key rules and
79 the timeline of routine events critical to Nextflow adoption.

80

81 **Rule 1: Develop a strategic plan aligned to the institutional priorities**

82 A well-designed capacity development program within any institute should (i) reflect the needs
83 of the institution and (ii) adhere to a well-scoped curriculum that benefits the entire organization.
84 Identifying core stakeholders and aligning the program with the institution's current and future data
85 analysis needs is essential for ensuring its long-term relevance and impact (Aron et al., 2021).

86 At The Kids, our vision is "Happy Healthy KIDS," and our objective is to enhance the health,
87 development, and lives of children and adolescents through exemplary research. Our work
88 encompasses a wide array of disciplines, from fundamental to applied science. In light of this diversity,
89 we have concentrated on research streams dependent on omics data processing, providing training for
90 students and EMCRs engaged in these data-intensive fields. We hosted an internal town hall meeting,
91 attended by research teams engaged in bioinformatics, as well as members of the Pawsey
92 Supercomputing Research Centre, an Australian government-supported high-performance computing
93 (HPC) facility. During this meeting, we documented common roadblocks and challenges experienced
94 by bioinformatic users, which laid the foundation for developing a strategic plan and the formation of
95 a special interest group (SIG) with focus on bioinformatics. Building on these insights, we established
96 a three-pillar strategy aimed at improving the efficiency, repeatability, and scalability of our
97 bioinformatics investigations. This strategy focuses on transitioning from ad-hoc shell scripts to the

98 integration of Nextflow workflow manager into our computational research (Sztuka et al., 2024) while
99 making the best use of shared resources.

- 100 **1. Pillar one** of our strategies involved identifying available computational resources,
101 understanding their allocation across the different research groups, and assessing existing
102 knowledge gaps and bioinformatics needs.
- 103 **2. Pillar two** focused on promoting a community of “power users” by integrating support and
104 mentorship. A mentorship program was established to guide EMCRs through their learning
105 journey, while promoting collaboration, a cornerstone of data-driven research. Researchers
106 were encouraged to share their experiences, common challenges, and best practices,
107 ultimately strengthening knowledge exchange, and sparking innovation with a strong,
108 supportive community.
- 109 **3. Pillar three** emphasized adherence to established standards and best practices. We
110 promoted the use of bioinformatics standards and provided templates and guidelines for
111 creating reproducible and well-documented Nextflow pipelines, thereby enhancing research
112 quality and credibility.

113 These three pillars informed the design of engagement activities, including seminars and online
114 tutorials (Rule 5), Hacky-Hours (Rule 6), one-on-one sessions and bootcamps (Rule 7). Additionally,
115 continuous evaluation and feedback (Rule 8 and 9) were pivotal in refining and adapting these activities
116 to meet the evolving needs of researchers effectively.

117 **Rule 2: Promote awareness of reproducible, robust and open science.**

118 Promoting awareness of reproducible data analysis and bioinformatics best practices is crucial
119 in “omics” fields like transcriptomics, genomics, proteomics, metabolomics, and microbiomics. As
120 researchers increasingly adopt “multi-omics” approaches to gain deeper insights into biological
121 phenomenon (Reel et al., 2021; Vahabi and Michailidis, 2022), the importance of reproducibility,
122 robustness and open science cannot be overstated. These practices ensure reliable and actionable
123 research findings while promoting transparency and allowing for validation, which is vital for scientific
124 progress (Kraus, 2014; Stewart et al., 2022). A successful implementation of the capacity-building
125 strategy (Rule 1) should ensure clear communication of the best bioinformatic practices. Participants
126 must understand the importance of these practices in programming and computational experiments,
127 such as testing simulations, algorithms, and models. Additionally, they should recognize the clear

128 benefits of applying these practices within the context of their own work and research groups. (Carey
129 and Papin, 2018; Heise et al., 2023).

130 At The Kids, we accomplished this through (i) direct approaches, using seminars and Hacky-
131 Hours, as well as (ii) indirectly through mailing lists and a dedicated Microsoft Teams channel. These
132 platforms allowed us to share relevant resources and promote awareness effectively.

133 **Rule 3: Identify the needs and skill gaps of different research groups within the institute**

134 The key to successful capacity building effort lies in understanding existing skills and
135 identifying future needs of research groups (Woelmer et al., 2021). We began by conducting an initial
136 survey aimed at comprehensively evaluating key requirements of the EMCRs (Supplemental Data S2).
137 The survey gathered information on (i) basic computational skills (e.g. Linux command line
138 proficiency or scripting using Python and/or R languages), (ii) familiarity with bioinformatics tools
139 and workflows; (iii) experience with Nextflow and nf-core; (iv) and specific challenges faced in their
140 research programs.

141 We encouraged participation by emphasizing the importance of the surveys in identifying
142 bioinformatic pipeline needs at The Kids, with weekly follow-ups over four weeks. This approach
143 ensured detailed and honest responses. The results provided an accurate overview of the current
144 bioinformatics capabilities and needs, and the insights shaped our implementation strategy, helping us
145 identify priority topics for training and skill development.

146 Using insights from the survey, we categorized researchers' skills into three levels (beginner,
147 intermediate, and advanced). This allowed us to design targeted training programs to address the
148 identified gaps by building upon the sensitize, train, hack and collaborate model (Karega et al., 2023).

- 149 1. **Beginner users** focused on basic skills and attended introductory courses on Linux,
150 bioinformatics fundamentals (Brandies and Hogg, 2021), and monitoring pipelines using
151 the Seqera Platform (<https://seqera.io/platform/>).
- 152 2. **Intermediate users** focused on workflow development with Nextflow and nf-core pipeline
153 templates (Roach et al., 2022).
- 154 3. **Advanced users** specialized in customizing existing nf-core pipelines and integrating new
155 tools for cluster systems, such as those provided within Australia by Australian Pawsey
156 Supercomputing Research Centre (Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre Perth, 2023d,

157 2023b, 2023c, 2023a) and the Australian BioCommons Leadership Share (ABLeS)
158 program (Gustafsson et al., 2023).

159 This targeted approach ensured that researchers received the precise support they needed to advance
160 their bioinformatics skills and progress efficiently within their research projects.

161 **Rule 4: Engage with the IT team for infrastructure automation and sustainability through**
162 **documentation (Nextflow-Biowiki).**

163 Building a sustainable bioinformatics environment requires close collaboration with the
164 Information Technology (IT) team. Their expertise in infrastructure management, data storage (short
165 and long-term), and data sharing and protection is invaluable for adhering to responsible big data
166 research practices (Zook et al., 2017). At The Kids, we partnered with the IT team to standardize and
167 streamline frequent computational requests for “omics” data analysis and to establish long-term storage
168 solutions for the Nextflow-Biowiki documentation created during the program (Agudelo-Romero et
169 al., 2023).

170 To optimize infrastructure, the IT team developed a baseline virtual machine (VM) template.
171 This template standardized configurations for efficient installation of the core dependencies, including
172 Java (LTS version) (Arnold et al., 2005), Nextflow (Di Tommaso et al., 2017), and nf-core (Ewels et
173 al., 2020). Package managers like Bioconda (Dale et al., 2018) and Mamba (mamba-Org, n.d.), and
174 containerization tools such as Docker (da Veiga Leprevost et al., 2017) and Singularity (Kurtzer et al.,
175 2017), were also preconfigured. Shared access to critical resources (*e.g.* genome reference files) was
176 enabled, and computing resources, such as number of CPU core, memory and disk space (scratch
177 workspaces), were allocated based on project-specific data and analysis needs. To ensure robustness,
178 we validated the setup by running various nf-core pipelines, addressing any issues, ensuring a seamless
179 performance, and securing enough storage to the outcome’s files on the VMs.

180 At the same time, to ensure long-term sustainability, we created comprehensive documentation
181 that could be used for future reference for EMCR and researchers’ community. We hosted the
182 Nextflow-BioWiki project (Agudelo-Romero et al., 2023) on The Kids’ institutional GitHub repository
183 (<https://github.com/TelethonKids>). This resource includes detailed guides on bioinformatics tools,
184 workflows execution, troubleshooting in our infrastructure, online manuals, video tutorials, and
185 Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs); catering to diverse learning styles. The documentation was
186 designed to be user-friendly and accessible to all researchers. Regular updates based on users’ feedback

187 have ensured that resources remain relevant and aligned with technological advancements and
188 community needs.

189 **Rule 5: Conduct regular seminars using relevant nf-core pipelines.**

190 Regular seminars aimed to introduce participants to conducting computational experiments
191 under optimal conditions (“the happy path”), focusing on data analysis and interpretation. For the
192 implementation of monthly seminars, we followed principles outlined by Fadlilmola et al 2019.
193 Seminars were designed to address real-world data analysis challenges, such as parameter optimization
194 and chaining multiple pipelines for comprehensive analyses.

195 At The Kids, regular seminars covered the breadth of available resources, as key references,
196 without overwhelming participants. These regular seminars also offered a unique opportunity to
197 increase awareness about the resources available from the Institute and the Nextflow and nf-core
198 communities, such as pipeline-specific “byte size” talks. To facilitate focused learning, we organized
199 dedicated seminars for “omics” pipelines under cohesive themes, including:

200 1. **Transcriptomics:** nf-core/rnaseq (Patel et al., 2024), nf-core/differentialabundance
201 (WackerO et al., 2023), nf-core/smrnaseq (Peltzer et al., 2024b).

202 2. **Methylation:** nf-core/methylseq (Ewels et al., 2024) , nf-core/atacseq (Patel et al., 2023).

203 3. **Microbiome:** nf-core/ampliseq (Straub et al., 2024) , nf-core/mag (Yates et al., 2024),
204 agudeloromero/everest_nf (Agudelo-Romero et al., 2025).

205 4. **Single-cell:** nf-core/scrnaseq (Peltzer et al., 2024a).

206 This thematic grouping allowed participants to dive deeper into specific areas, establishing a
207 better understanding of key biological concepts related to the “omics” strategies, while also
208 encouraging collaborations among students and EMCRs working on similar topics.

209 Ultimately, during our seminars, we encouraged participants to explore and embrace cloud
210 platforms as an integral part of their continued growth. Offering auxiliary opportunities for talent
211 enhancement and performing their data analysis in the cloud. Consequently, certain participants in this
212 program obtained research credits for performing their analysis and deploying Nextflow on cloud
213 infrastructure. Supplemental Table S1 delineates cloud computing companies that extend credits for
214 academic purposes.

215

216 **Rule 6: Organize practical training sessions (Hacky-Hours)**

217 While regular seminars introduce theoretical concepts, Hacky-Hours translate them into
218 practical skills through coordinated sessions tailored to the specific needs of EMCRs (Heise et al.,
219 2023). These sessions provide hands-on opportunities to address challenges such as accessing different
220 infrastructures or optimizing computing sources for diverse projects, empowering EMCRs to build
221 their analytical capacity effectively.

222 The involvement of the IT team and researchers in designing Hacky-Hours provided valuable
223 insight in the sessions. The IT team contributed by offering guidance on structured use of resources,
224 ensuring efficient resource allocation. Meanwhile, engaging with researchers helped identify
225 opportunities to refine the program's content. For instance, when a specific nf-core pipeline was
226 routinely used, an interactive Hacky-Hour session was organized on that pipeline. This session
227 included step-by-step instructions and troubleshooting, delivering practical and targeted training
228 (Boudabous and Tekaiia, 2020).

229 At The Kids, bi-weekly Hacky-Hours (30-90 minutes) were structured around topics identified
230 via participant surveys. Initially, these sessions focused on fundamental skills such as downloading
231 and configuring nf-core pipelines. As Nextflow and nf-core adoption grew, surveys revealed a growing
232 need for advanced topics like troubleshooting and handling complex configurations (Supplemental
233 Data S2). This iterative feedback process allowed us to adapt and prioritize future session, ensuring
234 relevance to the evolving needs of the community. Hacky-Hours were scheduled flexibly and only held
235 when there was clear interest, maximizing participation and avoiding unnecessary strain on
236 communication channels.

237 **Rule 7: Structured and Personalized Training**

238 To accommodate diverse skill levels and learning styles, a successful capacity-building
239 program should combine structured group training with personalized mentoring, such as bootcamps
240 and mentoring session, respectively. Bootcamps are an efficient way to immerse participants in the
241 theoretical and practical aspects, exposing them to the tools and techniques essential for modern
242 bioinformatics. While mentoring sessions is personalized approach empowered individuals to navigate
243 the complexities of bioinformatics.

244 At The Kids, we implemented an integrated approach that included immersive week-long
245 bootcamps alongside tailored one-to-one mentorship sessions. Bootcamps effectively introduced

246 participants, especially students and EMCRs, to the theoretical and practical aspects of Nextflow and
247 nf-core. These events balanced conceptual learning with hands-on pipeline development and included
248 dedicated "Bring Your Own Data" (BYO-D) sessions to ensure relevance to individual projects.
249 Including IT team members in these sessions fostered mutual understanding between researchers and
250 technical support, aligning infrastructure solutions with research needs.

251 To complement group training, we offered one-to-one mentoring tailored to participants with
252 limited bioinformatics experience or specific project challenges. Mentors from the organizing team
253 provided individualized support, helping participants gain confidence in using workflow tools. These
254 sessions also generated valuable feedback, which shaped and expanded the BioWiki documentation
255 (<https://github.com/TelethonKids/Nextflow-BioWiki>), ensuring it remained practical and user-
256 informed (McGrath et al., 2019). For broader reach, we recommend starting with foundational seminars
257 (Rule 5) and Hacky-Hours (Rule 6) before launching advanced bootcamps focused on troubleshooting
258 and complex configurations (Hagan et al., 2020). This layered approach promotes continuous learning
259 and maximizes long-term impact.

260 **Rule 8: Facilitate continuous learning and engagement**

261 To ensure the long-term success of the capacity development program and build a community
262 of "power-users," it's crucial to establish continual learning and engagement opportunities. Leveraging
263 internal platforms, such as messaging apps or newsletters, is an effective strategy for informing
264 participants about current activities and upcoming events. A monthly newsletter is also an effective
265 medium for sharing updates on Nextflow developments, like module binaries and wave containers, and
266 nf-core community projects, including new pipelines, modules, and configurations.

267 At The Kids, we established a Microsoft Teams channel as a space for discussion and promoted
268 a local volunteer community. The long-term success of the program depends on users willing to assist
269 each other in areas such as creating new software/pipelines (Brack et al., 2022), customizing existing
270 pipelines, addressing infrastructure questions, and designing bioinformatics experiments within the
271 infrastructure.

272 Beyond the internal communication, engagement with the global Nextflow and nf-core
273 communities is also encouraged and should be a major goal of the capacity-building program for long-
274 term success. Communities such as online forums offer valuable resources, this is demonstrated in the
275 nf-core Slack group (<https://nf-co.re/join>) and the organized community events, including online
276 training sessions (<https://nf-co.re/events/hackathon>). By participating in these community events,

277 researchers gain access to a wealth of knowledge and opportunities for collaboration. We anticipate
278 engagement with open-source communities like nf-core will become the standard for modern
279 bioinformatics.

280 **Rule 9: Assess the program design and implementation regularly.**

281 In our experience, a key factor in running a successful bioinformatics capacity development
282 program is to conduct regular assessments. Feedback from participants provided the organizing team
283 the opportunity to evaluate engagement levels and refine the program as needed. As the program
284 progresses, some participants may struggle to keep on track. To address this, we recommend
285 implementing quarterly checkpoints to ensure program objectives are being met.

286 These assessments should focus on three fundamental questions:

- 287 1. What is working?
- 288 2. What can be improved?
- 289 3. What should be discontinued in the next phase?

290 At The Kids, we used the initial survey (Rule-3) as a baseline and conducted regular evaluations
291 to gather participant feedback (Supplemental Data S2). This enabled us to track learning progression,
292 identify challenges, and refine training initiatives. Adjustments to internal communication strategies
293 were also made to ensure the program continued to meet the needs of EMCRs and aligned with the
294 institute's research goals. Our final survey provided valuable insights into the program's effectiveness
295 and participant engagement (Supplemental Data S3). It assessed whether we met our objectives and
296 successfully enhanced EMCR skills. Additionally, the final survey gave participants an opportunity to
297 reflect on their learning, reinforcing knowledge retention and paving the way for future capacity-
298 building initiatives.

299 **Conclusion**

300 In summary, our experience at The Kids demonstrates that integrating Nextflow and nf-core in
301 bioinformatics training significantly enhances research capacity. These platforms equip EMCRs to
302 navigate complex "omics" data analysis. By understanding computing environments and scientific
303 needs, we successfully implemented Nextflow and nf-core to improve technical capabilities and
304 promote continuous learning. This has been essential to ensure our research remains reproducible,
305 reliable, and ready for future bioinformatics challenges.

306 Investing in awareness campaigns, strategic planning, community engagement, and varied
307 training opportunities, including seminars, Hacky-Hours, mentorship programs, and bootcamps, yields
308 significant benefits. By fostering continuous learning and engagement, we have upskilled researchers
309 and built sustainable bioinformatics resources. We identified several opportunities for enhancing the
310 program and are excited to share the following recommendations for those planning similar initiatives
311 (Supplemental Table S2). Our program serves as a practical roadmap for institutions aiming to
312 strengthen bioinformatics capabilities and support cutting-edge research.

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433 **Figure and Table Legends**

434 **Figure 1.** Overview of the golden rules for building sustainable bioinformatics capacity using nextflow
435 and nf-core, with a focus on EMCRs. Based on the experience of The Kids, the process begins with
436 Rule 1 (Strategic Plan), Rule 2 (Promote Awareness), Rule 3 (Needs and Skill Gaps), and Rule 4
437 (Engagement with IT and Documentation). Various events described in the remaining rules are
438 distributed throughout the year, with key milestones highlighted in each quarter. This information is
439 documented in the Nextflow-BioWiki (<https://github.com/TelethonKids/Nextflow-BioWiki>)
440 (Agudelo-Romero et al., 2023).

441 **Table 1.** Summary of the motivation for the rules' development.

442

443 **Supplementary Material**

444 **Supplementary Figure S1** | Theme Collaboration Award members.

445 **Supplementary Figure S2** | Initial, Regular and Final Feedback Surveys for Capacity-Building
446 Assessment.

447 **Supplementary Figure S3** | Schedule for Nextflow Basic and Advanced Bootcamps.**Supplementary**
448 **Figure S4** | Non-Exhaustive List of National (Australia) and International Grant Calls for
449 Capacity Building.

450 **Supplemental Table S1** | Academic usage credits from cloud computing providers

451 **Supplemental Table S2** | Recommendations for Future Programs

452

453

454

Table 1. Summary of the motivation for the rules' development.

Motivation	Rule
Implementation	Rule 1 and 2
Knowledge gap	Rule 3
Resources	Rule 4
Support	Rule 5, 6, 7 and 8
Engagement and evaluation	Rule 9

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456

457 **Author Contributions**

458

459 PAR: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Resources, Supervision, Writing (original draft, review
460 & editing). TC: Resources, Writing (review & editing). JAC: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition,
461 Writing (original draft, review & editing). DJM: Funding acquisition, Writing (review & editing). AK:
462 Funding acquisition, Writing (review & editing). SMS: Funding acquisition, Writing (review &
463 editing). CH: Resources, Writing (review & editing). AS: Conceptualization, Resources, Writing
464 (original draft, review & editing).

465 **Conflict of Interest**

466 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
467 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

468

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